

Abstract

The emergence of modular "building blocks" for CNN allowed an easier complex feature extraction through stacked layers. This work investigates how the efficient use of building blocks in an image classification architecture helps achieving good accuracy while requiring fewer computational resources (GFLOPs).

Introduction

The design of neural network architectures evolved from individual neuron arrangement to large-scale abstractions (blocks). **Convolutional blocks are used in the initial stages of a CNN**, where the primary goal is to extract features from the input image. They are typically **repeated multiple times** in the network, with each block extracting more complex features from the output of the previous block. This **hierarchical structure** allows the network to learn increasingly complex features, leading to **improved image recognition performance**.

Our **objective is to compare the performance** of different convolutional blocks. As VGG is still largely used for image classification, we use its architecture as reference, replacing the original blocks with new ones.

Methodology

Using VGG as the main framework, we compare blocks from different architectures:

- VGG original block
- MobileNet (V1, V2, V3)
- ResNet V1
- Inception V1
- SqueezeNet
- GhostNet
- CGNet (segmentation)
- C2F (part of YOLOv8)
- Our own proposition:

Pooling pyramid with three successive 2x2 max-pooling layers

Training / Datasets

Benchmarks

- Small images
 - used as reference
 - Average-size images
 - adapted for tiny ML usages
 - **Larger images**
 - **similar to real applications**
- All models trained under the same conditions
- 500 epochs
- Cross entropy loss
- Adam optimizer

Small

MNIST
28x28x1, 10 classes

Fashion MNIST
28x28x1, 10 classes

Medium

CIFAR-10 / CIFAR-100
32x32x3, 10/100 classes

Tiny ImageNet
64x64x3, 200 classes

Large

ImageNet
160x160x3, 10 classes

ImageWoof
160x160x3, 10 classes

Results

Accuracy

MNIST / Fashion MNIST

- 90% or more accuracy for all blocks
- Non-representative (too easy)

CIFAR 10/100

- Inception V1 outperforms other blocks
- Classification is hard with low resolution and high number of classes (<40% CIFAR-100)

Tiny ImageNet

- Pooling pyramid block wins, but general accuracy remains low (<30%)

ImageNette / ImageWoof

- Pooling pyramid block wins again, reaching 78,5% on ImageNette and 66,4% on ImageWoof
- **Huge improvement** from the original VGG blocks

Resource Requirements

- Computing power (GFLOPs)
- Memory consumption (# parameters)

Conclusion

Adapting the models may bring **important reductions on memory and computing requirements**, free cores for other tasks. Recent block designs are especially interesting in the case of Edge or IoT applications that need to optimize the devices' resources and energy consumption.